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PARENTS AND THEIR WAY OF SHOPPING IN THE PRESENCE OF A PRESCHOOL CHILD

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Abstract

Consumption has become essential for community alliances, identity formation, lifestyle determination, differentiation from others and our place in society. Namely, the individual tries to shape his/her identity through the consumption of objects that have a meaning for him/her i.e. he/she interprets them as important for his/her idea of himself/herself (Luthar, 2002). However, the article presents an in-depth look at consumerism in the modern world, its presence in the family of a pre-school child and the factors of consumer socialization, and discusses the role of the family in this. The study examined and parents' responses to their children's ways of persuading them to buy regarding the gender and the current status of parents and the gender and the age of preschool children.

Keywords: childhood, consumerism, consumer socialization, family, the role of parents.

Introduction

The family has the greatest influence in the child's development and growing up. It is the primary environment in which the child usually spends the most time and is surrounded by his or her loved ones, whom he or she imitates the most, thereby acquiring and developing his or her characteristics and eventually the whole personality. The family is also the space where the child receives primary socialization, where he or she acquires values and norms and learns social relationships (Bezenšek, 2000: 35). In the pre-school period,

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family is even the most important factor in socialization, as the child acquires the basic experience, abilities and rights in it that he or she is supposed to develop (Hauptman & Komotar, 2010: 24). The important role of the family is also to set the boundaries of their needs and desires. Above all, a preschooler (in addition to praise and rewards) needs limitations in order to learn behaviour by testing them, also to feel protected, safe and loved. Of course, family members must be consistent and also adhere to restrictions. Children start growing up quickly and become more independent, but even then, parents need to stand by them, encourage them, and help them gain independence (Bezenšek, 2000: 10). The society we live in today has evolved to such an extent that adults need to teach preschoolers some of the pitfalls and threats of the globalized world. A potential pitfall is also consumerism and its impact on children's behaviour and emotions. Namely, the child's consumer behaviour also significantly shapes the family's shopping habits.

Consumption and consumer culture

In traditional hedonism, people used to buy goods to satisfy specific needs such as hunger, thirst, need for clothing and the like. In the traditional consumption, therefore, the basis was sensual satisfaction, while in the (post)modern, consumers strive for pleasure, and emotions are necessary to meet the needs (Corrigan, 2006: 15). Consumption or shopping has become one of the central (late) modern cultural practices, round which a whole range of human motivations, hopes, ambitions and aspirations revolve (Luthar & Ule, 1998: 9). In modern times, we are primarily looking for pleasure in all the experiences and moments of life, with consumerism also associated with pleasure, desire, taste, emotions, lifestyle, fashion, identity, subjectivity, it also affects ideology, hegemony, class society and class taste, money, exclusionary politics and technology. Emotions are key, but they need to be controlled, which was not known before and therefore people relied on a sensory stimulus (Corrigan, 2006; Luthar & Ule, 1998).

Consumption has become essential for community alliances, for identity formation, for determining lifestyles and for differentiating ourselves from others and our place in society. Namely, the individual tries to shape his identity through the consumption of objects that have a meaning for him i.e. he interprets them as important for his idea of himself (Luthar, 2002). Thus, the emergence

of modern consumer society has strongly marked and shaped the modern man and his society. To have comes to the fore, especially to have as much as possible and always something new. We no longer buy the product because we need it, but to get the experience that this product gives us. Even though a short-term experience.

Today, consumption is something so self-explanatory that we can talk about it as a way of life, but in essence, it is about consumer culture (Luthar, 2002). Specifically, Luthar (ibid: 146) states: "To speak of a culture as a consumer culture, the possibility of consumption must be extended to the whole population, and production must, in principle, be organized as the production of large series for delivery to the general population." The factors that triggered the emergence of a consumer society are numerous and intertwined. It emerged simultaneously with numerous economic and social changes. Sociologists agree that the beginning of the industrial society was in the first half of the 19th century or earlier, but they are not unanimous about the beginning of the consumer society. Many say that they would place the beginning at the end of World War II, after 1950, when Europe had to be rebuilt because of the aftermath of the war and people were able to afford many things that they had never even thought possible because of the rapid economic development. However, some believe that consumption started earlier (Corrigan, 2006: 2).

One of the visible signs of a global consumer culture are toys, games, movies, television, food and brands aimed at children. Childhood is a crucial moment for merchants and is already a huge trade target (Langer, 2004). The consumer culture deliberately targets children from an early age with messages about what is beautiful and who is popular, while at the same time creating materialistic and visual norms and values as the focal point of children's socialization (Banerjee & Dittmar, 2008: 175). As a result, childhood has become very commercialized, so children are no longer just outside observers of the consumer culture (Martens, et al., 2004). There is a direct link between toys as a central factor in childhood and productivity orientation of toy manufacturers (Langer, 2004). Manufacturers are aware that children are a very profitable market, even though they are only indirect consumers.

Consumer socialization

Consumer socialization is part of the overall socialization process. According to Ward (1974: 2), the consumer socialization is the process by which young people acquire skills, knowledge, and attitudes relevant to their functioning as consumers in the marketplace. It is therefore a process through which children learn about consumer behaviour. "While in the overall socialization we talk about a person being a member of the society as a result of the process, the consumer socialization results in the individual being a member of purchase and consumer processes, thus a part of the marketing. Consumer socialization is important for understanding how the culturally induced social norms are perceived by the consumer and how the consumer adapts and transforms them into the consumer behaviour" (Šramova, 2017: 94).

The consumer socialization became the interest of marketers and other professionals in the field in the 1970s (Gunter & Furnham, 1998). In the second half of the 20th century, entrepreneurs and advertisers began to place greater emphasis and interest on consumer socialization, as they realized that in the process, children begin to develop into future consumers, so they wanted to maximize their influence on their consumer experience and research.

The consumer socialization of children is influenced by many factors. Older literature emphasizes the role of parents, peers, and the mass media (Ward, 1974), while newer literature adds the influence of kindergarten and school (Gunter & Furnham, 1998) as well as shops and shopping centres (Šramova, 2017: 101). The most important socializing factors, however, are manifested in the frequency over a given period and the extent of their influence i.e. social power (Kuhlmann, 1983). The answer to a question as to when does the consumer socialization begin must be from the birth. The child acquires the first consumer experience in the family through clothing, food, toys, TV, or shopping with parents. In some sense, the child is a part of the social behaviour in the family even before the birth. Future parents prepare for their role very responsibly (Šramova, 2017: 99).

Parents proved to be one of the main socialization agents of children. This fact is in correspondence with the findings about parents and family are important economic socialization agents (Moschis, 1987;

Webley & Nyhus, 2006). The main reason parents have a dominant influence on the child is that different types of consumer behaviour are practiced in the family and children are able to observe and imitate it. The influence of the family on consumer socialization is often linked to social conditions such as household socio-economic status and gender and age of the child. (Gunter & Furnham, 1998). Before coming into contact with peers, children only look up to their parents, because most of the time they are with them, and therefore imitate them and take over their values and, consequently, their marks, as they see only their affection, which they also trust and do not doubt, since they do not know else. As a child grows up, as Ward (1974) points out, parental influence is declining and the influence of peers and the mass media is increasing. Already in kindergarten, peers and the media have a great influence on children, since they always compare toys with each other and watch commercials with toys and clothes for children, both in magazines and on television. McNeal (2007: 311) similarly established that parental influence is not always equally strong. We estimate that it is precisely during the preschool years that parents need to have the greatest influence on their children, talk to them about products, review commercials and watch television ads, so that they can be taught a critical view of advertising and consumption.

Nonetheless, it is also very important for children to become socialized consumers, since without this process they will not acquire the desirable knowledge and thus consumption experiences. All socialization factors co-shape a child's consumer behaviour, so it is very important in what kind of environment the child develops. Through this process, the child will learn to make responsible, rational and independent purchase in a positive and encouraging environment.

Methodology

Purpose of the research

With the empirical research, we wanted to study the influence of preschool children on parents' shopping habits and the parents' response to their children's ways of persuading them to buy, according to parental gender, parental status and the child's age.

The following research questions were posed:

Do you usually buy more than you planned in stores when you go there with your kids?

How does your child try to persuade you to buy the product he or she wants?

How do I usually react to the child's wishes in the store?

When a child sees a product that is visually appealing to her or him and asks you for it, you see that it is too expensive and you cannot afford it. How will you explain this to your child to understand?

Research method

We applied the descriptive and causal-non-experimental method of pedagogical empirical research.

Research sample

The study involved 120 parents of pre-school children of the first and second age group whose children were enrolled in the kindergartens of Maribor in the school year 2018/19.

Among the respondents, 81.7% were female and 18.3% male. We also divided the parents according to their current status and we found that the majority of respondents were married (52,5%) and the fewest (3,3 %) were single. None of them is widowed, but 6.7% were divorced, and 37.5% live in a common-law relationship.

We classified their children into six categories according to age: at the time of the survey, 5.0% of children were 1 year old, 13,3% of children 2 years old, 23,3% of children 3 years old, 21,7% of children 4 years old, 22,5% of children 5 years old, 22,5% of children 6 years old and 11,7% of children 7 years old.

Data collection and processing procedures

In the process of data collection, we used a questionnaire for parents of preschool children. All questions were closed-ended and also expressed with verbal and graded responses.

The data collected through the questionnaire were processed by computer using the SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) statistical program. Absolute (f) and percentage (f%) frequencies were determined for closed-ended questions and the data thus obtained presented in tables. The dependencies between these variables were tested with the χ^2 test.

Results and interpretation

In the study, we were interested in the influence of preschoolers on parents way of shopping, so we first checked with the respondents whether they went shopping with or without the children. In doing so, 55.8% of the respondents said that most often they go shopping with their children, while the rest (44.2%) said that they usually go shopping without the children.

In the following, we examined the difference in the amount of consumption of the parents surveyed with regard to the presence of their children when shopping. The analysis of the responses showed that more than half (55.0%) of the parents surveyed sometimes spend more, and as many as 25.8% of the respondents always spend more money or buy more products when they go shopping with their children. Only 19.2% of the parents surveyed said that when the children go shopping with them, they do not spend more money than usual. However, we expected more parents surveyed to circle "yes", but even the proportion of parents with such an answer indicates that the presence of a child when shopping is a decisive factor in the amount of money spent. And most often, parents spend more, not less.

We were also interested in whether there were any differences by gender and status of parents, as well as the gender and age of the preschooler.

Table 1: Analysis of the respondents' answers to the question "Do you usually buy more than you planned in stores when you go there with your kids?" by gender and status of parents and age of the child.

Purchase	Parents' gender		Parents' status*				Child's age in years							
	M	F	A	B	C	D	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Yes	f	7	24	14	14	0	3	1	1	8	6	9	6	0
	f%	31,8	24,5	31,1	22,2	0,0	37,5	16,7	6,3	28,6	23,1	33,3	42,9	0,0
Sometimes	f	6	60	25	36	3	2	4	13	15	16	12	5	1
	f%	27,3	61,2	55,6	57,1	75,0	25,0	66,7	81,3	53,6	61,5	44,4	35,7	33,3
No	f	9	14	6	13	1	3	1	2	5	4	6	3	2
	f%	40,9	14,3	13,3	20,6	25,0	37,5	16,7	12,5	17,9	15,4	22,2	21,4	66,7
Total	f	22	98	45	63	4	8	6	16	28	26	27	14	3
	f%	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

$\chi^2=10,783$ $\chi^2=6,257$ $\chi^2=14,087$
 $g=2$ $g=6$ $g=12$
 $P=0,005$ $P=0,395$ $P=0,295$

*Legend for the parental status: A – common-law relationship; B – married; C – single; D – divorced.

Based on the results (Table 1), we have found that a statistically significant difference existed only with respect to the gender of the parents ($P = 0.005$). A close look shows that fathers (31.8%) more often than mothers (24.5%) always buy more than they planned, when they take their children with them, while mothers (61.2%) more often than fathers (27.3%) do this occasionally, but not always. Interestingly, the "no" answer was also more often chosen by the fathers. No statistically significant differences were observed in the results by parental status and age of the child.

As we have already found, in many families children are involved or co-responsible for the amount of the purchase. Therefore, we were particularly interested in the ways in which the child convinces his or her parent to purchase the additional product he or she wants. We allowed the respondents to choose from 3 of the several statements offered, with which they agree. Not all respondents circled three ways, some only one or two.

Table 2: Absolute (f) and percentage (f%) frequencies of respondents to the question "How does your child try to persuade you to buy the product he or she wants?"

Children's ways of persuading to buy a product	f	f%
He/she asks if I buy him a product.	83	30,5
He/she repeatedly asks for a product.	74	27,2
He/she starts to spite.	35	12,9
He/she does not require.	27	9,9
He/she begins to cry.	23	8,5
He/she starts to scream and to draw the attention of other customers.	12	4,4
Other.	11	3,7
He/she requires me to buy the product.	8	2,9
Total	272	100

Based on the results (Table 2), we see that most (30.5%) of the respondents chose the assertion that the child asks them to buy him/her a product. They are followed by the respondents who indicated that the child begins to repeatedly ask for the product (27.2%). Fewer respondents agreed with the statement that a child requires a product purchase (2.9%) and other (3.7%), where they under "other" stated: that they already agreed on a purchase at home, that they would jointly make a compromise, that they would

talk at the store if the wanted product was really necessary for him/her, that the child would negotiate in the sense of 'if you buy me, I promise ...' or that all his friends had the product.

We took a closer look at whether there were statistically significant differences regarding convincing to buy a product by parental gender and status and age of children. As we have found, there are no statistically significant differences anywhere. However, when analysing this question, we found some interesting differences with respect to the gender of the respondent. Fathers are more likely to say that their children start screaming, thus attracting the attention of others, (33,3%) and that they try to get the product they want by crying (26,1%). Mothers, however, are quite divided: while they most often said that the child required the product (87,5%), on the other hand, almost 85.5% said that the child always asks for a product, as much as that he or she does not ask for the product at all. According to the age of the preschool child of the surveyed parents, we found that children 4 years of age or older are more likely to try to persuade the parents to buy by verbal convincing, while younger children are more likely to cry or spite. Besides all this, the reaction of parents is also important, which we were interested in below.

Table 3: Absolute (f) and percentage (f%) frequencies of respondents to the question " How do I usually react to the child's wishes in the store?"

Responses of the parents surveyed to their children's wishes	f	f %
I explain why I will not buy this product.	92	33,2
I say no and persist regardless of the child's behaviour.	55	19,9
I explain that I do not have enough money.	34	12,3
I promise to buy the product next time.	29	10,5
I satisfy my child's wishes and buy the product.	26	9,4
I say nothing, I ignore him/her.	21	7,6
I make up that I do not have enough money.	12	4,3
Other.	8	2,9
Total	277	100

We again allowed the interviewed parents to choose three already given answers, but some of them circled only one or two. Most often, the parents surveyed chose the statement that explain to the child why they would not buy him or her the chosen product (33,2%), the

second most common response is that they say no and persist in their response regardless of the child's behaviour (19,9%). The fewest respondents chose the answer that they make up that they had not got any money (4,3%), and other (2,9%), where they gave the following answers: I negotiate with the child about buying a product, which depends on the price and the child's wish, I usually buy him or her only one useful product, he or she has modest wishes such as a candy bar, in the case of a more expensive product, we agree to get it for the next holiday.

A closer examination did not show statistically significant differences with respect to the gender and status of the respondents, including the age of the children. However, some real differences have emerged: surveyed mothers responding to the child's requests most often react by saying that they do not have enough money (88,2%) and say no and insist on this (78,2%), while the surveyed fathers make up that they do not have enough money (41,7%) or they ignore the child (28,6%). Married parents surveyed most often promise to buy the product next time (62,1%) or they make up that they do not have enough money (75,0%), while the surveyed parents in a common-law relationship explain that they do not have enough money (41,2%) or they satisfy the child's wish and buy the product (34,6%). According to the age of the preschool children of the surveyed parents, we found that the parents of the three-year-olds most often say nothing and ignore the child (33,3%), the parents of the five-year-olds explain to the children that they do not have enough money (26,5%), and the parents of the four-year-olds promise to buy the product next time (24,1%). The age of the child is probably conditioned by the fact that parents do not explain to the younger, as they estimate that they do not understand, while to the older children they more often explain or talk to.

In the following, we asked the parents the question about a specific, very expensive product and how they act in such a case. As can be seen from the table below, most parents surveyed (63.3%) openly state that they do not have enough money at the moment and that they will probably get the desired product some another time. As many as 25.0% of those surveyed explain to their child that if they buy him this expensive product, he or she will not get other new toys for a while due to the high price.

Table 4: Absolute (f) and percentage (f%) frequencies of respondents to the question " When a child sees a product that is visually appealing to her or him and asks you for it, you see that it is too expensive and you cannot afford it. How will you explain this to your child to understand?"

Ways the interviewed parents explain that the product is too expensive	f	f%
I openly state that I do not have enough money at that moment and that he or she will probably get it some another time.	76	63,3
I explain to him or her that I can buy him this product, but because of such a high price he or she will not get other new toys for a while.	30	25,0
Nonetheless, I buy him or her that product, because, despite the high price of it, I want to fulfil his or her wish.	6	5,0
Other.	8	6,7
Total	120	100

Table 5: Analysis of the respondents' answers to the question "When a child sees a product that is visually appealing to her or him and asks you for it, you see that it is too expensive and you cannot afford it. How will you explain this to your child to understand?" by gender and status of parents and age of the child.

Explanation**	Parents' gender		Parents' status*				Child's age in years						
	M	Z	A	B	C	D	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
T1	f 11	65	32	37	1	6	5	11	19	13	15	11	2
	f% 50,0	66,3	71,1	58,7	25,0	75,0	83,3	68,8	67,9	50,0	55,6	78,6	66,7
T2	f 8	22	7	19	2	2	0	3	7	10	9	1	0
	f% 36,4	22,4	15,6	30,2	50,0	25,0	0,0	18,8	25,0	38,5	33,3	7,1	0,0
T3	f 2	4	1	4	1	0	0	2	1	2	0	1	0
	f% 9,1	4,1	2,2	6,3	25,0	0,0	0,0	12,5	3,6	7,7	0,0	7,1	0,0
T4	f 1	7	5	3	0	0	1	0	1	1	3	1	1
	f% 4,5	7,1	11,1	4,8	0,0	0,0	16,7	0,0	3,6	3,8	11,1	7,1	3,3
Total	f 22	98	45	63	4	8	6	16	28	26	27	14	3
	f% 100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	$\chi^2=3,231$	$\chi^2=12,017$	$\chi^2=19,874$										
	g=3	g=3	g=3										
	P=0,357	P=0,212	P=0,340										

Legend for the parental status: A – common-law relationship; B – married; C – single; D – divorced.

**Legend for the explanation: T1 – I openly state that I do not have enough money at that moment and that he or she will probably get it some another time. T2 – I explain to him or her that I can buy him this product, but because of such a high price he or she will not get other new toys for a while. T3 – Nonetheless, I buy him or her that product, because, despite the high price of it, I want to fulfil his or her wish. T4 – Other.

An in-depth analysis reveals that there are no statistically significant differences in the justification for refusing to buy the desired (too)expensive product by parental gender and status and age of the child. Nevertheless, it can be seen from the data obtained that only the single parents surveyed most often (50.0%) explain to their child that they can buy the product they want, but because of the high price, they will not get other new toys for a while. Most of the other parents surveyed stated that they react most often by telling the child openly that they did not have enough money at the moment and that he or she would get the product another time. According to the gender of the respondents, it is noticed that women are more likely to postpone the purchase (66.3%) and men are more likely to buy immediately with the condition that there will be no other toys for some time (36.4%).

Discussion and conclusion

Already at the beginning of our study, we found that just over a half of the parents surveyed take their children often with them when they go shopping. The data obtained are positive in this regard that almost half of the parents surveyed (in our case 44.2%) most often do not take their preschooler with them when they go shopping. From this we can assume that they do not expose their child to consumerism to often. On the other hand, the contact with consumerism is important because it is inevitable and therefore all the more important to start with proper education in the field of consumerism even in the child's earliest stages.

The extent to which a child is involved in family shopping habits is influenced by several factors. The factors are often related to demographic conditions such as socio-economic status of the family,

gender and age of the child (Gunter & Furnham, 1988). Of course, this begs the question of whether it makes sense to take a preschooler with us every time we go shopping. The advantage of shopping with parents, however, is that they accustom the child to rational shopping and that he or she can observe the entire purchasing process, from picking goods, comparing brand prices, to cash register activities where they can see the exchange of money for goods. Over time, the child will gain insight into the value of money and its role in life choices. McNeal (2000) explains that succeeding in the consumer role is crucial to an individual's basic well-being. Parents know this, which is why in our society they often encourage their children to participate as consumers. As soon as possible, they take the child with them to shop and thereby enabling them to observe the activities there and make proposals for purchase. As soon as they know how to articulate their wishes, they are given the possibility to choose products. They then give them money so they can spend it and learn the basics of spending money.

Of course, a prerequisite for a child to gain insight into rational and efficient shopping is the parent's expert knowledge of it and their actual proper behaviour and functioning in the shopping process. »Preschoolers constantly observe and imitate their parents, so they are also their role models in developing the consumer behaviour i.e. the consumer identity. Consumerism exists and will exist in the future. We cannot deny it, but we can learn to behave and act properly. Therefore, the important task of parents is also to socialize children in the existing consumer society to the extent that this child will in the future develop into a critical consumer, able to judge what he really needs« (Hmelak & Oprešnik, 2018). There are the direct and the indirect influence. We talk about the direct influence of parents on children when parents try to educate children about their own consumer values. It is a direct instrumental learning where parents try to encourage certain behaviours with conviction. The indirect influence of the family on consumer socialization is manifested in the child's observing and imitating his or her parents' behaviour (McNeal, 2000; Gunter & Furnham, 1988; Solomon, Bamossy & Askegaard, 2006; Prosenc, 2005). Otherwise, the child will get a distorted pattern and notions of shopping, and each time shopping with children will cause conflicts, blackmail, conditioning, crying, anger and aggression on the part of the child as well as the adult.

Further, we examined the difference in the amount of consumption of the surveyed parents with regard to the presence of children in shopping. Based on the results obtained, we found statistically significant differences with respect to the gender of the parents. As it turned out, there are, on the one hand, either very indulgent fathers who always buy more when their children are with them, or fathers who never buy more and therefore the presence of a child does not affect their decision to buy. Mothers, however, are the ones who most often marked the answer "sometimes". In general, we find a different pattern of shopping based on the gender of the parent.

When we asked the parents about the ways their children persuade them to buy the desired product, there were no statistically significant differences, but an interesting factual difference was revealed with respect to the gender of the respondents. Based on the respondents' answers, we conclude that, with screaming and crying as a means of blackmail, children are more successful with their fathers, while with mothers, the focus is more often on verbal persuasion or demand for purchase. In addition to the claims offered, the respondents also wrote their own suggestions, which we presented in the results. In any case, the way preschool children will react to a possible rejection and how they will try to achieve the purchase of the product they want depends on the type of upbringing they have. However, it is important for parents to be consistent in their explanations and reasoning if they want the child to learn appropriate shopping behaviour.

Among other things, we found that, when the child wishes to buy an (too)expensive product, parents generally refuse to purchase such an item, explaining that they currently have no money but allow the possibility of a later purchase. As much as a quarter of them buys the product immediately, but adds that in such case, the child will not get a new product in a while. As we can see, parents are honest with a child, which is important. The child needs to be explained the situation as it is, regardless of his or her age. But what is more problematic is that they buy the product (immediately or once in the future) and thus in no case deny the child the possibility to buy it. Although this option was not given, interestingly no one wrote that they do not buy the product or just say to the child, "I will not" or "I do not want to". Even those who opted for the answer "other" did not mention these options, but they merely stated their excuses for

postponing (but not refusing) the purchase of a (too)expensive product.

We find that parents, along with their preschool children, are frequent consumers and that, especially when shopping together, they spend more money or buy more products. Even more. The role of the child in the shopping process is increasing and in many families the child becomes more important than the parent as he or she becomes the purchase decision maker. With her or his wishes and demands, as well as persistent and successful ways of satisfying them, the child significantly contributes to the consumer habits of his or her family. Of course, to the extent to which parents allow them to do so and give in to their demands. As Moore (1993) points out, in childhood, the parental influence is of paramount importance in shaping consumer values. In early childhood, children identify with their parents, imitate them and behave as their parents dictate, so it is no wonder that they soon learn what (according to their parents' belief) proper behaviour is.

Resources

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